

THE ROLE OF EPISTEMOLOGICAL RESEARCH IN DEVELOPING LOGICAL AND CRITICAL THINKING AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE

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Annotation: This article highlights that the development of logical thinking and critical reasoning among the younger generation has become one of the most pressing pedagogical and philosophical issues under the current conditions of globalization and informatization. It also emphasizes that epistemological research, namely scientific approaches related to the theory of knowledge, provides an important methodological foundation for this process. Furthermore, the article analyzes how epistemological views contribute to the development of young people's thinking by encouraging them to analyze knowledge, evaluate it, and make independent conclusions.

Keywords: gnoseology, gnoseological research, logical thinking, critical thinking, artificial intelligence, media literacy, information.

INTRODUCTION. Following the achievement of independence philosophical thinking in our country rose to a new stage. Ideological restrictions were removed and national approaches were formed. All necessary conditions for the development of science were created and significant investments were made in all areas of science. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated in his speeches: "Science is the foundation of progress. Neither the state nor society has a future without relying on the achievements of modern science and innovative ideas" [1]. From this perspective, the role of epistemological research in developing logical thinking and critical reasoning among young people occupies a special place. It serves to foster independent thinking in the younger generation, develop skills of critical information analysis, and enhance the ability to draw conclusions based on knowledge and evidence.

METHODS. The problem of the development of logical thinking and critical thinking in young people was studied on the basis of various scientific sources and theoretical views. For example, such scientific works as N. Shermammedova's "Gnoseology: Theory of Knowledge," I. Yusupov's "Foundations of Gnoseology," T. Xo'janova's "Socio-Philosophical Analysis of Protecting the Youth of Uzbekistan from Ideological Aggression in the Era of Information Warfare," K. Abdukarimov's "Media Literacy as a Means of Combating Disinformation," B. Ziyatova's "The Philosophical, Psychological and Didactic Essence of Innovative Thinking," and A. Qodirov's "Today's Philosophy: Causes of Decline and Factors of Rise" are considered important sources for our research.

During the research, the methods of synthesis and analysis, comparative analysis, historical approach, system analysis, and observation were effectively used.

RESULTS. In today's modern world, acquiring knowledge is not just about collecting information. In the current era, where information technologies and the digital environment are highly developed, learning is a process of analyzing information, selecting it, and applying it in practice. A person must be able to critically evaluate any information and determine its reliability. Therefore, today, the acquisition of knowledge is considered an important process

that ensures an individual's intellectual development, social activity, and professional competitiveness.

The widespread integration of powerful computer technologies into education and the process of cognition is creating new opportunities for learning, thinking, and cognitive development. However, this process is also giving rise to a number of negative consequences that affect the deeper layers of human thought.

N. Shermammedova states in the book "Gnoseology – Theory of Knowledge" as follows: "Researchers have identified several complex problems in the formation of 'computer consciousness' and cognition. One of them is a 'consumerist attitude' toward the computer and, as a result, the emergence of certain negative aspects of thinking. In particular, these include the weakening of critical ability, neglecting the emotional side of cognition and the creative foundation as irrational factors that cannot be formalized, the loss of a historical approach to phenomena, and the impoverishment of the user's language" [2].

Researcher T. Xo'janova notes that strategic approaches to combating the negative impact of modern information technologies include three important directions. First, it is necessary to develop special skills in young people that enable them to respond to situations arising in the modern information environment. Second, it is important to familiarize them with methods of conducting dialogue and open discussion on complex issues between different cultures and civilizations. Third, developing the ability of the younger generation to engage in theoretical thinking is regarded as one of the main priorities [3].

Indeed, as a result of the widespread use of the internet, social networks, and artificial intelligence technologies, humanity has gained free access to an unprecedented volume of information. However, along with this opportunity, the problem of determining the reliability, truthfulness, and objectivity of information is becoming increasingly acute. From this perspective, gnoseology appears not only as a theory explaining the process of acquiring knowledge, but also as a methodological foundation for distinguishing truth in the modern information environment.

At the same time, the concept of media literacy is emerging as an integral part of critical thinking. Media literacy is not simply the ability to read or view information, but the ability to understand, analyze, evaluate, and use it consciously. In today's information society, this skill plays a decisive role in shaping young people's critical thinking and logical reasoning.

First of all, the essence of media literacy is that a person does not accept any information as truth without careful thought and instead examines it critically.

In other words, information is examined by asking such questions as: "Where was this information obtained from?", "What is the author's purpose?", and "How reliable is the evidence presented?" In this respect, media literacy represents a practical form of the gnoseological process and increases the activity of the subject of cognition.

T. Xo'janova's research explains that the main aim of information wars is to influence public thinking. This can happen not only by giving false information or hiding the truth, but also by stopping the process in which information becomes knowledge in the human mind [4.18].

Another important part of media literacy is checking sources. For example, when a young person sees news, they should not believe it immediately. They should check other independent sources to see if the same information is there. This is a clear example of critical thinking.

Otherwise, they can become a victim of false information. Emotional and sensational news that spreads quickly on social media is often not checked.

Philologist K. Abdukarimova, in her study “Media Literacy as a Tool Against Disinformation”, says that the media environment is becoming too full of information, which increases fake news and false information. This creates risks for mental health and social unity. In such conditions, media literacy becomes an important way to protect people from manipulation. It helps users evaluate information critically and take part in forming public opinion [5.5].

Media literacy is an important life skill for modern youth. It helps them move safely through the flow of information, find the truth, and think independently. Through this skill, a person changes from a passive consumer into an active, aware, and critical thinker.

Researcher B. Ziyatova emphasizes that human behavior and motivation also play an important role in the formation of innovative thinking, that applying existing knowledge in practice is a complex process, and that society’s acceptance of new knowledge, philosophical ideas, technologies, and methods often occurs with difficulty, creating strong psychological pressure on the subjects of innovative thinking [6]. Indeed, as gnoseology studies the essence, stages, and subjective factors of the process of cognition, it serves as a theoretical and methodological foundation for developing young people’s innovative thinking.

Certainly, a person’s free and independent thinking depends on gnoseological factors such as knowledge, belief, emotional state, and attitude toward cognition. “Human thinking is influenced not only by one’s knowledge, the analytical and generalizing capacity of the mind, the courage to take responsibility for making independent conclusions, healthy skepticism, and emotional-psychological characteristics, but also by one’s faith and attitude toward certain religious-philosophical, aesthetic, and moral systems of values” [7.49]. This idea means that human thinking is formed not only through knowledge and logic, but also through the courage to draw independent conclusions, reasoned doubt, emotional condition, and religious-philosophical as well as moral values.

Undoubtedly, gnoseological research plays an invaluable role in developing young people’s critical thinking and logical reasoning. Anvar Qodirov, Doctor of Philosophy and Professor, states that contemporary philosophy appears to be experiencing a deep decline, losing its traditional methodological potential, and seeming to lose its relevance[8.81]. The main solution to the decline in philosophy emphasized by Professor Anvar Qodirov is directly connected with freedom of thought. However, freedom of thought does not arise on its own; it is formed through logical reasoning and critical thinking.

Logical thinking teaches a person to think consistently based on evidence and arguments, while critical thinking makes it possible to question existing views, analyze them, and evaluate them. Only when these two factors are combined can philosophy restore its methodological strength, overcome its state of decline, and become an important force for the development of social thought.

DISCUSSION. The formation of logical reasoning and critical thinking in young people has strategic importance in the context of modern development. In today’s complex and rapidly changing flow of information, every individual must be able to understand events and phenomena deeply, express an independent attitude toward different ideas and views, and

draw well-grounded conclusions. Such intellectual qualities do not emerge by chance, but are formed through consistent learning, an analytical approach, and conscious thinking.

Therefore, an important task of the educational process is to foster a culture of thinking among young people, help them learn to reason logically and based on evidence, and develop their skills in selecting, analyzing, and evaluating information. As result, it becomes possible to raise a well-rounded generation that thinks innovatively, feels social responsibility, remains open to new ideas, and can succeed in a competitive environment.

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